

Quantum Dynamical Probability Wave

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A classical particle is considered to be a point described by $x(t)$ i.e. x and t are both a set of points. In a one dimensional problem, however, $dx = v(x) dt$ so if all dx tend to zero, then dt 's are small, but don't tend to zero in the same way. In other words dx may be considered small, but of a finite size. To have a particle within dx , it should have a probability distribution that goes to zero at the endpoints of dx i.e. one could have a repeated set of these for a constant velocity. This, however, contradicts $P(x) = C_1 dt = C_1 dx/v(x)$. Thus it seems first that there are two kinds of probability distributions and that the set of distributions fitting into each dx is incomplete because if this set is described by a function $F(x)$, this function should have the same magnitude at $F(x+dx)$ for a free particle. This suggests a phase function linear in x i.e. $\exp(i C_1 x)$.

$P(x) = C_1 dx/v(x)$ is based on dynamics and no dynamics appears in $\exp(i C_1 x)$. It seems that dynamics should occur leading to the possibility of $\exp(i p x)$. (This, however, is ad hoc.) We call this a dynamic probability as opposed to $P(x)$. In quantum mechanics it is called a wavefunction. If one considers the classical free action (relativistic or nonrelativistic) with x and t independent, then $A = -Et + px$ (1) and one may create eigenvalue equations $-i\partial/\partial x \text{ partial } \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA)$ and $i\partial/\partial t \text{ partial } \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA)$ so $\exp(ipx)$ also appears more formally.

In other words a fixed resolution periodic distribution requires the same shifted distribution (i.e. $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$) kept as separate dimensions i.e. "i" in order to create a dynamic probability which is a phase function which may be linked to $P(x)$. This phase function $\exp(ipx)$, however, consists of two classical-like waves showing that in each dimension probability is "carved" out of troughs and added to crests. The two dimensions allow for the dynamic probability to be consistent with $P(x) = \text{constant}$ for a free particle.

Classical Action and Waves

The classical action for a free particle (relativistic $A = -m_0 t \sqrt{1-vv}$ ($c=1$)) or ($A = t .5 mvv$) with $v=x/t$ may be varied independently in terms of x and t to yield:

$$dA/dx \text{ partial} = p \text{ and } dA/dt \text{ partial} = -E \text{ or } A = -Et + px \text{ ((1))}$$

For $dA = 0 = -E dt + p dx$ one finds that $dx/dt = v = E/p$ which is a classical wave solution. A classical wave may be described by $\cos(-Et+px)$.

((1)), however, may be written as an eigenvalue equation:

$$-i \partial/\partial x \text{ partial } \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA) \text{ and } i \partial/\partial t \text{ partial } \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA) \text{ ((2))}$$

A question arises, however, namely: Why does one want a eigenvalue equation? We see later that this solution is linked to a dynamical probability.

The Importance of Dynamics on Probability

A classical particle moving in a potential $V(x)$ has a velocity $v(x)$ such that Energy = $.5m v(x)v(x) + V(x)$. In a small constant dx , $dx=v(x) dt$ so $dt = dx/v(x)$ which is taken to be proportional to $P(x)$ i.e. the probability for the particle to be within dx at x . Thus $P(x)$ is dependent on dynamics even for a free particle. Furthermore dx is not really a point, but a small distance.

Quantum mechanics deals with probabilities. Furthermore $P(x)=$ constant for a free particle. The question which arises is where are the dynamics? This brings one to ((2)) i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ which is dynamical. It is composed of $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ the shifted wave in a second dimension. Thus to incorporate dynamics within probability, one needs to have a two dimensional probability object representing the particle at t_1 and t_2 . In quantum mechanics, the particle is not a point, but a wave much like the classical wave except that the wave is a probabilistic one. $\cos(-Et+px)$ from $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is exactly the classical solution, but $P(x)=1$ whereas $P(x) =A \cos(-Et+px)$ for the classical wave. Thus $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is new object which we call a dynamical probability or wavefunction. It consists of a classical type wave $\cos(-Et+px)$ plus its shifted value at a later time such that:

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx)^* \exp(-iEt+ipx) = 1 \quad ((3))$$

((3)) is required because $P(x) =$ constant for a freely moving particle.

As argued one cannot arrive at this result without dynamics. The dynamics in quantum mechanics are of a wave type, thus one has positive and negative $\cos(-Et+px)$ values, but one also needs a spatially shifted solution to show the movement because there is no medium with crests and troughs for a freely moving particle. The two probability wave components, however, are very much like a classical wave in the sense that they interfere.

Wavelength Versus a Point

Classical mechanics describes a particle as a point $x(t)$. Thus both x and t represent points, but this contradicts the above section for which a classical density $P(x) = C_1 dt = C_1 dx/v(x)$. Dt and dx would have to be zero. In calculus they tend to zero, but dt at t_1 is not the same as dt at t_2 so dt is a finite length, albeit very small. The same holds for dx . For a particle to be with dx one needs a distribution which drops to zero at the start and end points of dx . For an overall probability, one might think of a set of distributions with tiny dx widths, one after the other. The problem is that this is biased because the distribution is 0 at the start and end points of dx , but all x points should have equal probability for a free particle. This is based on $dt = c_1 dx/v$ where $v=$ constant so one needs dynamics. One may have this set of distributions if one also has another set representing the system at a different time. This forces one to keep the two distributions separate i.e. use two dimensions.

The question is how one represents motion. If one considers motion as a periodic process i.e. maps it into a rotation then $\exp(ipx)$ is a solution such that px is the angle of rotation. As described above, one may have a set of distributions around the dx 's, but overall this must be a

function of x i.e. $F(x)$. If one writes $F(x+dx)$ one cannot obtain a result with a different modulus. This suggests that $F(x)$ is a complex function of the form $\exp(i C_1 x)$ for a free particle. X appears in a linear manner. This should also be linked to dynamics suggesting $\exp(i px)$ which matches ((2)).

The Role of Time

$\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ contains both t and x , but from ((2)) these are independent. Time t is associated with a frequency proportional to $1/E$ and is not linked to dynamics i.e. a shift in position. Thus $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ represent the free particle at different times, but this is not t as in $\exp(-iEt)$.

Consider $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$. These are the dynamic probabilities of p and $-p$, but they are not the same because the dynamics differ. One represents motion to the right and the other to the left. Thus we argue the two dimensions are linked to the describing the motion. $\cos(px)$ is a distribution with a bias, but $\sin(px)$ in the second dimension accounts for this bias and creates the modulus of 1. Thus it is not enough to have only a repeated or periodic probability distribution of $\cos(px)$, one needs the second dimension to show motion.

A particle's energy, however, is not smeared out over the wavelength, rather its probability is. If the particle collides with another at any x , the full impact of p is felt. Probability, however, governs how likely it is to find the particle and this is composed of two parts. The first is due to the wave like motion of $\cos(px)$, the second is due to the relative height of $W^*(x)W(x)$ at different peaks. As the energy level increases an envelope touching the waves approximates $c_1 dx / v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is classical velocity. Thus if one only considered the envelope, then $P(x)$ is proportional to the amount of time the particle spends at each dx and is not related to wave motion. The quantum dynamical wave motion is linked with the dropping portions of the humps which reach zero before increasing again.

Positive and Negative Momenta

Given that one has a wavefunction that is a dynamic probability, $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ differ. In fact, adding the two yields imaginary parts which cancel. $\cos(px)$ adds because each starts with the same probability profile, but changes in time differently. $\cos(px)$ which shows that a free particle is not a point, but rather has structure over a length proportional to $1/p$ i.e. the wavelength. This is linked to physical density. For example, if one has a distribution: $W(x) = \sum_{\text{over } p} a(p) \exp(ipx)$ then

$$W^*(x)W(x) = \sum_{\text{over } p} a^*(p)a(p) + \sum_{\text{over } p_1 \neq p_2} a^*(p_1)a(p_2) \exp(-ip_1 x) \exp(ip_2 x) \quad ((4))$$

The interfering second term on the RHs has positive and negative values which represent humps and troughs taken from the first term probability which does not depend on x . The classical wave type of behaviour occurs at the $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ level with probability being the medium i.e. the first term on the RHS representing probability which may be removed or be added to at different x points.

Thus it seems that free particle motion in quantum mechanics is a wave-like process and not the simple translation of a point as in classical mechanics. For the free particle $dt = dx/v$ ($v=\text{constant}$) which is proportional to $P(x)$. Quantum mechanics must use dynamics to produce this same result even within a wave framework for which one there are crests and troughs.

Increasing Energy and Resolution

The free particle shows that an increasing kinetic energy is linked to increasing resolution from $\exp(ipx)$. This idea also holds for a bound distribution with a potential $V(x)$ because one also has humps (e.g. in the quantum oscillator). Mathematically, the time-independent Schrodinger equation has orthogonal solutions and increased periodicity is one way to ensure such orthogonality already at the $\cos(px)$ level. As a result, for an oscillator an even solution with a hump at $x=0$ becomes an odd function with this hump splitting into two and leading to increased energy and resolution.

Conclusion

$P(x) = C_1 dx/|v(x)| = C_1 dt$ where $v(x)$ is the classical velocity. Classical mechanics, however, is not concerned with probability, but with $x(t)$. The probability picture, however, leads to a distribution of narrow humps with dx as the base (i.e. the distribution reaching zero at the endpoints of dx). This contradicts $P(x)=\text{constant}$ for a free particle. Furthermore if the periodic hump scenario is treated as $F(x)$ then $F(x+dx)$ should not have a larger or smaller modulus for a free particle. This suggests a dynamical probability which is a phase function linear in x i.e. $\exp(i C_1 x)$. From the classical action for a free particle with x and t independent i.e. $A = -Et + px$ one may create the eigenvalue equations $-id/dx \text{ partial } \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA)$ and $id/dt \text{ partial } \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA)$. Thus $\exp(ipx)$ serves as the dynamic probability of a free particle. We argue that this is like adding a periodic distribution set $\cos(px)$ with a shifted set $\sin(px)$ such that the modulus becomes 1 for a free particle. Thus in order to incorporate dynamics into a dynamical probability one must consider the distribution at two different times so to speak. For example if p is very large then $\cos(px)$ represents very narrow crests or troughs with widths approximately dx , but this does not show how the particle moves. It is the motion which establishes $P(x)=\text{constant} = c_1 dx/ v$ where $v=\text{constant velocity}$. The positive and negative parts of $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ show classical wavelike motion in a probability context which becomes explicit when one writes $W^*(x)W(x)$.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Lagrangian/Action Formalism as a Flow Scheme? (preprint, zenodo, 2021)